

UNLOCKING DATA

Canada

GUIDANCE NOTE

AN APPLIED DESIGN-BASED IMPLEMENTATION RESEARCH FRAMEWORK FOR THE UNLOCKING DATA INITIATIVE

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About the Unlocking Data Initiative

The Unlocking Data Initiative is a community of practice that connects African scholars, NGOs, national statistics offices and policymakers for the purpose of improving access to and use of education data. The **Unlocking Data: Scaling Uses and Users of Education Data** project is a collaborative work led by Zizi Afrique Foundation and supported by Education Sub-Saharan Africa, eBase Africa, University of Malawi's Centre for Education Research and Training (CERT). The latter project, which is being implemented in Cameroon, Kenya and Malawi, aims to scale up uses and users of data to address the knowledge gap of how to adaptively scale up the effective use of existing education data by policymakers and researchers in Africa.

To find out more about us, go to <https://unlockingdata.africa/>. Our evidence library can be found at <https://docs.unlockingdata.africa/lib/>

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CoL	Communities of Learning
CoP	Communities of Practice
DBIR	Design-based implementation research
EMIS	Education management information systems
MEL	Monitoring, valueation and learning
MINEDUB	Ministry of Basic Education (Cameroon)
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
PASEC	Program for the Analysis of Educational Systems of CONFEMEN
UDI	Unlocking Data Initiative

1. Introduction

This document provides practical guidance on how design-based implementation research (DBIR) is applied within the Unlocking Data Initiative (UDI). It is intended to support country teams, partners, researchers, and policymakers in understanding, designing, and implementing DBIR processes that strengthen access to, use of, and learning from education data (particularly at sub-national and middle-tier levels in education systems).

Drawing on UDI's experience across multiple country contexts, this guidance note sets out the rationale for using DBIR, clarifies its operationalisation in practice, and outlines the core phases, roles, and learning processes that underpin UDI's approach. Moreover, this document complements UDI's country-level DBIR reports and has been designed to serve as a reference across education data-focused system-strengthening project lifecycles, from initial system diagnosis and co-design through to implementation, reflection, and adaptive scaling.

1.1. Why use DBIR to 'unlock' data?

Across many African education systems, substantial volumes of education data are routinely collected through administrative systems, assessments, surveys, and project-based initiatives led by governments, civil society organisations, research institutions, and development partners. Despite this abundance, education data remains insufficiently utilised in decision-making. Data is often fragmented across institutions, inaccessible to key users, not considered credible, or poorly aligned with the practical decisions policymakers, implementers, and practitioners face. These challenges are particularly acute at sub-national and middle-tier levels (such as regional, county, district, or municipal structures) where planning, resourcing, coordination, and implementation decisions directly affect schools, teachers, and learners ([↑Development Gateway, 2024](#); [↑Fishman et al., 2013](#)).

UDI responds to this challenge by focusing not only on what data exists but also on how data is accessed, interpreted, processed, and used by policymakers, researchers, and practitioners. These challenges are not only technical; they are shaped by institutional incentives, capacity constraints, and fragmented systems. Moreover, weak feedback loops between data producers and data users, limited analytical capacity, and misaligned institutional incentives often mean that evidence generated across an education ecosystem does not meaningfully inform action or resource allocation ([↑Fotso et al., 2025](#); [↑Gachoki et al., 2025](#); [↑Twabi et al., 2025](#)). As a result, DBIR offers a practical approach for understanding and addressing operational challenges because it:

- Engages directly with persistent problems of practice within real education systems;
- Recognises that effective data use requires iterative design, learning, and adaptation, rather than one-off pilots or linear reforms;
- Centres co-creation with system actors, ensuring that solutions are feasible, legitimate, and contextually grounded;
- Builds both usable solutions and system capacity simultaneously;
- Generates learning that supports adaptive scaling, transferring core principles and functions while adapting tools and processes to the local context rather than replication of fixed models.

Within UDI, DBIR is used as a systems-strengthening approach that bridges research, implementation, and policy, with a particular focus on sub-national decision-making and middle-tier institutions.

1.2 Research questions and objectives

The DBIR approach within UDI is guided by a set of interrelated research questions and objectives that reflect the Initiative's focus on strengthening education data use as a system-level practice. Rather than seeking to test a single intervention or generate generalisable causal estimates, UDI's DBIR approach is oriented towards understanding how education data systems function in practice, and how they can be adapted to better support evidence-informed decision-making across diverse contexts.

The research questions and objectives are intentionally framed to support learning through implementation, recognising that answers emerge iteratively across DBIR cycles as actors engage with real constraints, incentives, and opportunities within education systems ([Fishman et al., 2013](#)). Across countries and DBIR cycles, UDI's work is guided by the following core research questions

- How can the UDI approach be effectively scaled at sub-national levels to strengthen policymakers' and researchers' capacity to access and use foundational learning data?
- What are the most effective ways to scale up the UDI approach in a new geography with no existing forum for convening data producers and users?
- How can a pan-African community of learning support the democratisation of data and evidence use?

- How can approaches to data collection, analysis, use, and sharing on foundational learning be made equitable and inclusive in terms of gender, geography, stakeholder group, and other inequality measures?

In response to the research questions highlighted above, the DBIR approach within UDI pursues the following objectives:

- Building knowledge on the most effective ways to scale the UDI approach.
- Strengthening the capacity of policymakers and researchers to access and use data on foundational learning for policy formulation and implementation.
- Facilitating knowledge mobilisation through national and pan-African communities of learning (CoLs).
- Building knowledge on how to make approaches to data collection, analysis, use, and sharing on foundational learning, equitable and inclusive.

By clarifying the rationale, objectives, and application of UDI, the guidance note aims to support coherence and shared understanding across countries and partners, and enable learning generated through DBIR cycles to be systematically documented, mobilised, and applied. It is intended as a practical reference document for country teams, partners, researchers, and policymakers, translating UDI's DBIR approach into actionable guidance that can be applied across diverse contexts while remaining responsive to local system dynamics.

1.3. Structure of the document

The guidance note is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** introduces the rationale for DBIR within UDI, outlines core research questions and objectives, and explains how the guidance should be used.
- **Section 2** defines what DBIR means in the UDI context, clarifying how it is applied in practice and how it differs from other research or implementation approaches.
- **Section 3** describes the core phases of the UDI DBIR cycle, highlighting typical activities, outputs, and learning processes across cycles.
- **Section 4** outlines the types of outputs and learning products generated through DBIR, including both tangible system outputs and less visible forms of learning that support adaptation and scale.

- **Section 5** examines ethical, relational, and practical considerations in conducting DBIR, including power dynamics, data protection, expectation management, and the avoidance of extractive research practices.
- **Section 6** looks ahead to how DBIR supports adaptive scaling across cycles and countries, the role of regional and pan-African Communities of Learning, and the positioning of UDI's DBIR approach as a transferable public good.

2. Defining DBIR for the UDI context

DBIR is an approach that integrates research, design, and implementation to address complex, persistent problems within real-world systems. It emerged in response to the limitations of traditional research and reform approaches, which often produce strong evidence but struggle to influence practice at scale (↑Fishman et al., 2013).

DBIR recognises that education systems are complex, adaptive, and socially embedded. Change within such systems does not occur through linear pathways, nor can it be achieved solely by introducing technical solutions. Instead, DBIR emphasises iterative cycles of inquiry, design, testing, and adaptation, carried out in close collaboration with the actors who work within and shape the system (↑Fishman et al., 2013); ↑Penuel et al., 2011).

Within DBIR, research is not positioned as a detached activity that precedes implementation. Rather, evidence is generated *through* implementation, with learning continuously informing the redesign of tools, processes, and strategies. This makes DBIR particularly well suited to addressing challenges related to system functioning, institutional behaviour, and capacity development.

2.1. DBIR as a bridge between evidence, implementation, and policy

UDI engages with education systems in which decision-making is often constrained not by the absence of information, but by the conditions under which evidence is produced, shared, and used. Data frequently travels through complex institutional pathways, shaped by organisational mandates, professional norms, and power dynamics that influence whose evidence is valued, when it is considered, and how it informs action (↑Fotso et al., 2025; ↑Gachoki et al., 2025; ↑Twabi et al., 2025). In these environments, fragmentation across actors, uneven analytical capacity, and limited opportunities for collective sensemaking weaken the links between evidence and policy or practice, particularly at sub-national levels where implementation decisions are most acute.

As a result, the DBIR approach is appropriate for UDI for several interrelated reasons:

- **Data use is a systems problem:** Improving data use requires changes to routines, relationships, and governance arrangements, not just the introduction of new tools or platforms. DBIR provides a framework for working with these systemic dimensions in practice (↑Fishman et al., 2013).
- **Education data ecosystems are multi-actor and fragmented:** In many contexts, governments, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), research

institutions, and development partners generate parallel datasets that are rarely integrated. DBIR allows UDI to engage these actors collaboratively, recognising that meaningful data use depends on coordination and trust across the ecosystem ([↑Fotso et al., 2025](#); [↑Gachoki et al., 2025](#); [↑Twabi et al., 2025](#)).

- **Sub-national contexts require adaptation, not replication:** Evidence from education reform shows that approaches that work in one context often fail when transferred without adaptation ([↑Andrews et al., 2017](#)). DBIR supports context-sensitive design and adaptive scaling, rather than fixed models.
- **Capacity-building must be embedded in daily practice:** Standalone training rarely leads to sustained changes in practice. DBIR integrates capacity-building into ongoing design and implementation processes, allowing skills and confidence to develop through use ([↑World Bank, 2022](#)).

2.2. Core principles of DBIR as applied in UDI

UDI's DBIR approach is informed by four foundational principles articulated in the DBIR literature ([↑Fishman et al., 2013](#)), and adapted to the Initiative's focus on education data use as explained below:

- **A focus on persistent problems of practice:** DBIR within UDI begins with challenges identified by system actors themselves (such as fragmented data systems, low demand for data, or limited analytical capacity) rather than externally defined solutions.
- **Commitment to collaborative and iterative design:** Solutions are co-designed with policymakers, practitioners, researchers, and non-state actors, and refined across cycles based on what is learnt during implementation.
- **Systematic inquiry to build practical and theoretical knowledge:** DBIR generates evidence about *what* works, *how* it works, and *why* it works in specific contexts, contributing to broader learning on strengthening education data systems.
- **Capacity-building for sustaining change:** Attention is given to building individual and institutional capacity so that improvements in data use can be maintained beyond the life of a specific project or pilot.

These principles ensure that DBIR functions not only as a research approach but as a mechanism for system strengthening.

2.3. DBIR entry points within UDI

In UDI's approach, DBIR does not begin from a single, predetermined starting point. Instead, it is deliberately designed to enter education systems through strategic entry points that reflect local priorities, institutional readiness, and existing relationships. These entry points serve as practical footholds for engaging system actors, surfacing persistent problems of practice, and initiating cycles of collaborative learning and adaptation.

Selecting an appropriate entry point is a critical design decision. Entry points shape who is engaged, which data is prioritised, how problems are framed, and the pace at which learning and change can occur. In contexts where trust is low or capacity is uneven, beginning with modest, clearly bounded entry points can help establish credibility and momentum before more complex system adaptations are attempted (↑Fishman et al., 2013; ↑Penuel et al., 2011). Across UDI's experience, DBIR entry points commonly fall into several overlapping categories, as highlighted in Table 1 below.

Table 1. DBIR entry points and examples

System condition or design consideration	Suitable DBIR entry point	Illustrative UDI example
Limited shared understanding of how data is produced, accessed, or used	Diagnostics and system reviews	Malawi – DBIR Cycle 1 prioritised analysis of administrative and assessment data systems to understand misalignment affecting learner progression analysis.
Strong demand from sub-national actors to use data for planning or allocation	Sub-national planning and coordination structures	Kenya – DBIR work engaged county and sub-county planning processes, creating demand-led pathways for dashboard co-design and testing.
Fragmentation and low trust across data producers and users	Communities of Practice (CoPs)	Cameroon – Regional CoPs were established to build trust, improve coordination, and align on shared priorities before introducing technical solutions.
Need for simple, usable tools to support specific decisions	Dashboards, portals, or harmonised tools	Kenya – Prototype dashboards were co-designed with county officials to support planning and service delivery decisions.
Capacity constraints linked to real data-use tasks	Task-linked capacity-building	Malawi – Capacity development occurred through hands-on engagement with existing data systems rather than stand-alone training.

Generally, DBIR entry points within UDI are not fixed or mutually exclusive. As DBIR cycles progress, new entry points may emerge, while initial ones may recede in importance. For example, diagnostic work may give way to tool piloting, or CoPs may

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become the primary space for reflection and adaptation. DBIR's flexibility allows these shifts to occur intentionally, guided by learning rather than predetermined plans.

By treating entry points as adaptive design choices rather than rigid starting points, UDI ensures that DBIR remains responsive to context, supports inclusive engagement among actors, and creates multiple pathways to strengthen access to, use of, and learning from education data.

3. The UDI DBIR Cycle: Core phases

DBIR is implemented through iterative cycles of inquiry, design, action, and reflection, with each cycle producing usable outputs and documented learning that inform the next cycle. While the emphasis of each phase may vary by country, context, and level of system readiness, the DBIR cycle provides a shared structure that supports coherence, comparability, and cumulative learning across UDI contexts. In UDI, a ‘cycle’ is treated as a time-bound learning and implementation period (ranging from 6 to 12 months) with a clear transition point at which stakeholders agree on what will be adapted, continued, or stopped.

This section discusses the phases of the DBIR cycles as applied to UDI. It highlights how these can overlap, repeat, or evolve as learning accumulates and system conditions change. The cycle provides a common learning approach, rather than a fixed implementation blueprint.

Figure 1. UDI DBIR cycle
 Source: Adapted from [†]Boehm (1988)

Figure 1 above illustrates the iterative DBIR cycle. It shows how learning, design, and implementation evolve through repeated cycles rather than in a linear sequence of steps. At the centre of the diagram is *analysis of the situation*, which represents the collective sensemaking that underpins the entire DBIR process. This step is about understanding how data is produced and used, identifying priority challenges in foundational learning,

and agreeing on actionable responses. This shared learning remains constant across all phases.

Moving outwards in a spiral, the diagram depicts four core phases:

- 1. Planning and preparation:** This phase focuses on problem diagnosis & system mapping, and understanding the education data ecosystem. Stakeholders jointly identify system challenges through consultations, situational analyses, and mapping of data flows, roles, and decision-making processes.
- 2. Identifying and resolving risks through a co-design process:** Building on the diagnosis, stakeholders collaboratively design and prioritise tools, processes, or approaches to address the identified challenges. The emphasis is on feasible, context-appropriate solutions rather than fully formed or final designs.
- 3. Initial implementation & embedded capacity development:** Co-designed solutions are tested in real conditions. Implementation is deliberately limited and purposeful, allowing actors to engage with live data and real decisions. Capacity is developed through use (by working with data, tools, and processes in everyday practice).
- 4. Evaluation, reflection, learning & adaptation:** Stakeholders jointly reflect on what worked, what did not, and why. This learning informs adaptations to designs, assumptions, and approaches before the next cycle begins.

The spiral structure conveys two important ideas:

- Each cycle builds on the previous one, expanding in scope and reach over time.
- Cumulative cost and effort increase as solutions move from diagnosis and prototyping towards broader implementation and potential scale.

Overall, the diagram highlights DBIR as a learning-centred, system-embedded process that prioritises collaboration, iteration, and the practical use of data to strengthen decision-making for foundational learning.

3.1. Phase 1: Planning and preparation

The first phase focuses on developing a shared and grounded understanding of the education data ecosystem within a given context. Rather than starting with predefined solutions, DBIR prioritises diagnosing persistent problems of practice as experienced by system actors themselves. Key objectives of this phase include:

- Understanding how data is currently produced, shared, and used;

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- Identifying institutional roles, incentives, and constraints;
- Surfacing fragmentation, duplication, or gaps across data sources;
- Clarifying which decisions data is expected to inform, and where breakdowns occur.

For UDI, the country situational analysis reports ([↑Gachoki & Arisa, 2025](#); [↑Kadzamira et al., 2025](#); [↑Pambe et al., 2025](#)) were among the first substantive outputs of the Initiative. These situational analyses were developed to map existing foundational learning data and knowledge ecosystems, identify key actors and data flows, and surface persistent challenges related to data fragmentation, access, trust, and use. They also created a shared evidence base from which subsequent DBIR cycles could be co-designed, informed the selection of priority actors and sub-national focus areas, and helped anchor collaborative discussions in locally grounded system realities.

In this way, the situational analyses functioned not only as analytical products but as catalysts for collective sensemaking and iterative design within UDI's DBIR approach. Findings from this phase are summarised below:

- **Data availability is not the main constraint:** Significant volumes of foundational learning data exist, but challenges lie in access, coordination, trust, and practical use (especially at sub-national and middle-tier levels).
- **Fragmented data ecosystems limit usability:** Administrative, assessment, survey, and project-based data systems operate in parallel with weak alignment, making synthesis and decision-relevant analysis difficult.
- **Sub-national actors are central but under-supported:** County, district, and regional actors play a key role in planning and implementation, but often lack timely, usable data and structured opportunities for sensemaking.
- **Capacity gaps are systemic:** Weak data use reflects institutional constraints (roles, incentives, routines, coordination) as well as individual skills. Training is rarely embedded in real tasks.
- **Trust and feedback loops are weak across the ecosystem:** Limited data sharing, concerns about data quality and ownership, and weak collaboration between government, researchers, and civil society organisations constrain evidence use.
- **Knowledge on foundational learning is uneven and inequitable:** Evidence is concentrated in certain regions and domains (e.g. literacy over numeracy), with limited coverage of marginalised populations and inclusive learning needs.

Overall, the findings highlight that iterative, system-embedded approaches that prioritise diagnosis, co-design, CoPs, and learning through implementation as foundations for sustainable scaling.

3.2. Phase 2: Identifying and resolving risks

Building on the diagnostic phase, DBIR moves into collaborative design. Phase 2 focuses on jointly identifying and shaping responses to the challenges surfaced in Phase 1, ensuring that emerging solutions are feasible, relevant, and contextually appropriate. Key objectives of this phase include:

- Translating diagnostic insights into design priorities;
- Clarifying what can realistically be tested or adapted within the system;
- Aligning expectations, roles, and responsibilities among stakeholders;
- Designing interventions that respond to both technical and institutional constraints.

For example, in Kenya, DBIR Cycle 1 involved the co-design of prototype county-level dashboards focused on foundational learning indicators ([†Gachoki et al., 2025](#)). This process emerged directly from engagement with county education officials, who articulated the need for simple, disaggregated data products to support decisions related to teacher deployment, infrastructure gaps, and service coverage. The dashboard prototypes were developed alongside efforts to harmonise the data collection tools used by different actors, revealing underlying challenges of fragmentation, duplication, and inconsistent reporting requirements across organisations working in the same schools. This co-design process illustrates how DBIR uses tool development to surface deeper system questions, ensuring that data products evolve in response to real user needs and constraints rather than being introduced as externally defined solutions.

In Malawi, co-design focused on collaboratively interrogating existing data systems and analytical practices to identify feasible pathways for improvement ([†Twabi et al., 2025](#)). Stakeholders worked together to examine indicator definitions, data structures, and reporting workflows related to learner progression and foundational learning. Through these discussions, participants prioritised areas where better alignment and coordination across data sources could strengthen analysis and use, particularly for planning and technical units. The co-design process emphasised incremental adaptation of existing systems rather than introducing new tools, ensuring that proposed solutions were grounded in institutional realities and could be taken forward in subsequent DBIR cycles.

The co-design process in Cameroon was anchored in a structured, participatory approach that brought together national and regional actors from the Ministry of Basic

Education (MINEDUB), statisticians, researchers, and civil society organisations (†[Fotso et al., 2025](#)). Through a national and regional stakeholders' workshop, participants jointly examined gaps in foundational learning data, reflected on the limitations of existing data sources such as the ministry's education management information system EMIS (SIGE) and identified shared priorities for strengthening data use.

3.3. Phase 3: Implementation and embedded capacity development

This phase focuses on testing co-designed solutions in real system conditions. Rather than a large-scale rollout, this phase typically involves limited, purposeful implementation intended to generate learning about feasibility, usability, and alignment with institutional routines. The objectives of this phase include:

- Understanding how proposed solutions function in practice;
- Observing how actors interact with data, tools, or processes;
- Identifying capacity gaps or enabling factors as they arise;
- Supporting learning through use rather than stand-alone training.

Communities of Practice (CoPs) are a core feature of the DBIR approach and a central pillar of UDI's sustainability strategy. All country teams fostered CoPs as part of their implementation approach, and these communities function as enduring learning infrastructures through which data use is normalised, relationships are strengthened, and collective problem-solving is sustained over time. They have proven to be particularly critical in contexts where challenges related to data use are relational, institutional, or trust-based, and where technical solutions alone are insufficient.

For example, in Cameroon, DBIR Cycle 1 was structured around the establishment of regional CoPs in the Centre and Northwest Regions, formally led by MINEDUB Regional Delegates (†[Fotso et al., 2025](#)). These CoPs functioned as sub-national coordination and learning platforms, bringing together diverse stakeholders to jointly examine data gaps, discuss the limited availability of learning attainment data, and co-create a manifesto defining shared objectives, roles, and ways of working.

Similarly, the team in Kenya fostered CoPs through repeated, structured engagement with county and sub-county education actors, particularly in Marsabit County (†[Gachoki et al., 2025](#)). Through these engagements, participants collectively identified priority data needs for county-level planning, resource allocation, and service delivery. Over time, these interactions helped build shared understanding and trust among actors, laying the

groundwork for more formalised approaches and structures to strengthen sub-national data use.

In Malawi, the development of CoPs centred on strengthening coordination and shared learning across institutions responsible for education data production and use ([↑Twabi et al., 2025](#)). DBIR Cycle 1 engagements brought together actors working with administrative and assessment data to jointly examine data structures, indicators, and system interfaces related to foundational learning. Rather than establishing a new standalone forum, the CoP approach in Malawi was embedded within existing institutional relationships, supporting sustained dialogue and learning that could inform subsequent DBIR cycles and future system-strengthening efforts.

Across the three countries, CoPs took different forms (formal, informal, embedded). These variations reflect context-specific pathways to achieve the same core function: creating durable spaces for joint analysis, learning, and adaptation.

Within UDI's DBIR processes, such CoPs provide structured and recurring spaces to embed reflection and learning within these communities. UDI supports the institutionalisation of data-informed practice beyond individual projects or cycles, ensuring that learning continues as systems evolve.

3.4. Phase 4: Evaluation, reflection, learning, and adaptation

The final phase of each DBIR cycle centres on structured reflection and learning, ensuring that insights from implementation are captured and used to inform subsequent cycles. Key objectives of this phase are:

- Assessing what worked, what did not, and why;
- Examining underlying assumptions about data use and system behaviour;
- Identifying design elements that require adaptation or abandonment;
- Informing decisions about scaling, replication, or redesign.

The key lessons from the first cycle of the DBIR are summarised below.

Cameroon

- **Foundational learning data is limited and unevenly prioritised:** While administrative data (EMIS/SIGE) is available, data on learning outcomes (particularly literacy and numeracy) is scarce and not systematically used in planning.

- **High fragmentation and weak integration across data sources:** Data from EMIS, national statistics, international assessments (e.g. PASEC¹), and local studies are not well integrated, limiting their collective usefulness.
- **Trust deficits constrain collaboration:** Policymakers expressed scepticism about the relevance and quality of independent research, while researchers raised concerns about access to and reliability of government data, weakening evidence-informed dialogue.
- **Sub-national actors lack analytical capacity and support:** Regional education officials have limited training and support to analyse and interpret data, constraining their ability to inform regional planning and feed insights upward.
- **Communities of Practice are a critical response mechanism:** The establishment of regional Communities of Practice was identified as a key strategy to address fragmentation, build trust, and create structured spaces for collaborative data reflection.

Kenya

- **Strong demand for data at the sub-national level, but low usability:** County and sub-county education officials expressed clear demand for data to support planning, resource allocation, and service delivery, but existing data were fragmented, outdated, or difficult to interpret for decision-making.
- **Fragmentation across actors collecting similar data:** Multiple actors (government, NGOs, programmes) collect overlapping school-level data using different tools, leading to duplication, reporting fatigue, and inconsistent datasets that are hard to reconcile at the county level.
- **Data use is constrained by infrastructure and access gaps:** Limited access to computers, connectivity, and analytical tools (particularly in marginalised counties such as Marsabit) restricts routine data use, even where data exists.
- **Capacity challenges are practical and task-specific:** Officials reported low confidence in analysing and visualising data, particularly disaggregated data needed for equity-focused decisions (e.g., teacher deployment, infrastructure gaps), highlighting the need for task-linked support rather than generic training.

¹ The Programme for the Analysis of Education Systems of the Conference of Ministers of Education of French-speaking States and Governments (PASEC), assesses the performance, efficiency, and equity of primary education in member countries.

- **Simple, user-oriented data products are preferred:** There was a strong preference for simple dashboards and harmonised tools that align directly with county responsibilities, rather than complex analytical platforms.

Malawi

- **Data systems exist but are poorly aligned with analytical needs:** Administrative and assessment data are routinely collected, but their structure, indicators, and reporting formats are poorly aligned with tracking learner progression and foundational learning outcomes.
- **Institutional coordination is a major bottleneck:** Roles and responsibilities across institutions involved in data production, validation, and use are not clearly defined, limiting effective data consolidation and analysis for planning purposes.
- **Capacity gaps reflect system design, not just skills:** Challenges in data use stem largely from unclear workflows, limited feedback loops, and weak integration across systems, rather than a simple lack of individual technical skills.
- **Limited use of data for adaptive decision-making:** Data is primarily used for reporting and compliance, with few opportunities or incentives to use it analytically to inform programme adaptation or policy decisions.
- **Need for incremental adaptation rather than new tools:** Stakeholders emphasised improving alignment and use of existing systems over introducing new platforms, underscoring the importance of co-design and gradual system strengthening.

Cross-country patterns from Cycle 1:

1. Fragmentation across data sources and actors is a common barrier
2. Sub-national actors face practical constraints (access, tools, time) and need task-linked support
3. Trust and feedback loops constrain collaboration
4. Foundational learning outcome data is limited / uneven
5. CoPs are a recurring mechanism for addressing these barriers.

4. What DBIR produces: Outputs and learning

The DBIR approach can also produce a diverse set of outputs that go beyond conventional research deliverables. These outputs are intentionally designed to support use, learning, and adaptation within education systems, recognising that sustainable improvement in data use depends as much on relationships, routines, and shared understanding as on technical products.

UDI's DBIR outputs can be understood across three interrelated categories: practical outputs for system use, learning-oriented outputs, and knowledge products that support adaptation and scale. These categories overlap by design; a single product (e.g., a dashboard) may also function as a learning device and platform for collaboration

4.1. Practical outputs for system use

These are concrete artefacts co-developed with system actors to respond to identified needs and decision-making contexts. Each practical output should be linked to a defined decision use case (who uses it, for what decision, at what point in the planning cycle) and a clear owner responsible for maintenance beyond the DBIR cycle. These outputs are often the most visible products of DBIR cycles and serve as practical entry points for improving data use. Some examples from UDI include:

- Situational analyses and system diagnostics that map foundational learning data ecosystems, actors, data flows, and decision points. These also inform prioritisation of entry points.
- Co-designed tools and products, such as dashboards, harmonised data collection templates, indicator frameworks, or analytical guides, which can inform sub-national planning.
- Governance and coordination artefacts, including the CoP or CoL manifestos, terms of reference, learning agendas, and operating principles to guide coordination of efforts.
- Synthesis reports, briefs, and presentations that consolidate learning for policymakers, practitioners, and partners.

These outputs are deliberately shaped through iterative design and stakeholder engagement, ensuring they are usable, contextually grounded, and aligned with existing institutional processes, rather than externally imposed or technically optimal but impractical.

4.2. Learning-oriented outputs

Equally central to DBIR are the learning-oriented outputs that emerge from collaboration, reflection, and implementation. While less tangible than tools or reports, these outputs are often the most critical for sustaining change. Examples of key learning-oriented outputs include:

- Shared understanding of system constraints, trade-offs, and priorities related to foundational learning data.
- Improved trust and working relationships across government, research institutions, civil society, and development partners.
- Increased confidence and fluency among policymakers and practitioners in interpreting and discussing data.
- Emergent routines and norms for collective data reflection and evidence-informed discussion.
- Clarification of roles and responsibilities in data production, analysis, and use.

These outputs help shift data use from individual or project-based activities to a collective, institutionalised practice, which is essential for sustainability.

4.3. Learning for adaptation and iteration

DBIR places strong emphasis on systematically capturing learning that informs adaptation across cycles. As such, many outputs function explicitly as learning products that capture insights about implementation processes and system behaviour. These learning products include:

- Documentation of what worked, what did not, and why during DBIR cycles (cycle reports).
- Identification of design assumptions that proved unrealistic or incomplete.
- Insights into conditions that enable or constrain data use, such as leadership support, incentives, or coordination mechanisms.
- Refined problem statements and design principles to guide subsequent cycles.

Rather than aiming for final or definitive solutions, these outputs provide design knowledge that helps actors make better decisions about how to adapt tools, processes, and approaches over time.

4.4. Implications for mobilising outputs and monitoring, evaluation, and learning

The DBIR approach prioritises learning, adaptation, and system change, and so the way outputs are mobilised and monitored extends beyond traditional dissemination and reporting approaches. Within UDI, DBIR outputs are most effective when they are treated as living resources, i.e., used, revisited, and refined through ongoing engagement with system actors rather than simply produced as end-of-cycle deliverables.

Mobilising DBIR outputs, therefore, focuses on embedding learning within existing decision-making and learning spaces, particularly CoPs / CoLs, where insights can inform practice and evolve over time. Monitoring and evaluation (MEL) similarly emphasises understanding how change happens, not just whether activities were completed. MEL plays a dual role: supporting accountability while also enabling reflection, adaptation, and cross-country learning across DBIR cycles. This includes tracking (i) process indicators (participation, cadence, tool usage), (ii) learning indicators (documented adaptations and tested assumptions), and (iii) harvested outcomes (observable changes in routines, decisions, coordination, and trust)

4.4.1 Integrating Outcome Harvesting within DBIR-aligned MEL

Alongside DBIR, UDI applies an Outcome Harvesting approach to capture changes that emerge through iterative, system-embedded work. Outcome Harvesting is particularly well suited to DBIR because many of the most important results (such as shifts in relationships, routines, confidence, and decision-making) are not fully predictable at the outset and may emerge unevenly across contexts. This approach complements DBIR by systematically identifying, verifying, and interpreting observable changes in behaviour, practice, or institutional processes resulting from DBIR activities. While DBIR provides the structure for learning through diagnosis, co-design, implementation, and reflection, Outcome Harvesting helps make visible *what changed, for whom, and how DBIR contributed* to those changes. In UDI, Outcome Harvesting should be planned as part of the cycle calendar (e.g., mid-cycle and end-of-cycle), led by the MEL focal person with participation of CoP / CoL members, and verified through document review and interviews with knowledgeable informants.

Together, DBIR and Outcome Harvesting support a MEL approach that balances intentional learning and accountability. DBIR guides what is tested and adapted over time, while Outcome Harvesting captures unanticipated outcomes and strengthens evidence about contribution rather than attribution. This integrated approach is particularly important in complex education systems, where change rarely follows linear pathways. Therefore, UDI's MEL approach combines process-oriented indicators with

harvested outcomes such as documented changes in how data is used in planning, coordination, or decision-making (e.g., adoption and routine use of dashboards in planning, revised reporting practices and documented collaboration agreements or joint analysis routines emerging from co-design), evidence of new or strengthened collaboration across actors involved in co-design, and so on. [Box 1](#) provides an overview of the steps for Outcome Harvesting as applied to UDI.

Box 1. *Outcome Harvesting in the Unlocking Data Initiative*

Outcome Harvesting is an evaluation and learning approach that focuses on identifying and understanding what has changed as a result of an initiative, rather than measuring progress solely against predefined indicators (↑Wilson-Grau & Britt, 2012). It is particularly well suited to complex systems, where outcomes are often emergent, non-linear, and difficult to predict in advance (↑Wilson-Grau, 2018).

Within the Unlocking Data Initiative, Outcome Harvesting is used alongside DBIR to capture changes such as shifts in how data is used, improvements in coordination and trust, or the establishment of new routines and practices. These outcomes may include changes in behaviour, relationships, institutional processes, or decision-making, and are identified through structured reflection and engagement with stakeholders rather than assumed at the outset. Outcome Harvesting typically involves four core steps:

- Identifying observable changes that have occurred;
- Formulating clear outcome statements;
- Verifying these outcomes with knowledgeable informants;
- Analysing how and to what extent programme activities contributed to these changes (↑Wilson-Grau, 2018).

By combining Outcome Harvesting with DBIR, UDI can make visible the learning and system changes that occur through iterative, collaborative work to strengthen both accountability and learning, and support adaptive scaling across contexts.

5. Ethical, relational and practical considerations in DBIR

The UDI approach (and its application of DBIR) is inherently relational and embedded in systems. This section considers ethical and practical considerations to ensure that DBIR processes are inclusive, responsible, and grounded in respect for system actors and communities.

5.1. Power and positionality in co-creation processes

Although DBIR emphasises collaboration and co-creation, power asymmetries inevitably shape who participates, whose knowledge is prioritised, and which decisions are ultimately taken. Differences in institutional authority, technical expertise, control over resources, and proximity to decision-making can influence DBIR processes in subtle but consequential ways. UDI's DBIR approach, therefore, emphasises active attention to power and positionality, including:

- Designing facilitation processes that enable meaningful participation from sub-national actors, researchers, and practitioners who may hold less formal authority, including: (i) the use of joint workshops for shared analysis, (ii) where appropriate, separate stakeholder engagements to surface constraints safely and reduce the effects of hierarchy.
- Being explicit about decision-making boundaries, recognising that not all co-design spaces carry the same level of influence (e.g., what can be decided within the co-design space versus what requires formal approval).
- Valuing experiential, contextual, and practitioner knowledge alongside technical and analytical expertise.
- Reflecting critically on how UDI and its partners position themselves within national and sub-national systems.

5.2. Data protection, privacy, and responsible use

DBIR often involves engagement with sensitive administrative, institutional, and, in some contexts, learner-level data. Ethical practice, therefore, depends on clear commitments to data protection, privacy, and responsible use, operationalised in day-to-day DBIR work. Within UDI, this includes:

- Compliance with national data protection laws and relevant ministry protocols.

- Clear agreements on data access, ownership, storage, and sharing.
- Minimising the use of personally identifiable data wherever possible and applying de-identification and aggregation when individual-level records are not essential.
- Ensuring that data is used only for agreed purposes.
- Communicating transparently with stakeholders about how data will be analysed and shared, including any limitations or risks.

5.3. Managing expectations in iterative and adaptive work

DBIR is deliberately iterative and exploratory. While this enables learning and adaptation, it can also create tension with expectations for rapid, tangible results. Without careful communication, DBIR risks being misunderstood as either too slow, insufficiently decisive, or overly academic. UDI addresses this by:

- Clearly framing early DBIR cycles as learning- and diagnosis-oriented with explicit end-of-cycle decisions (adapt / continue / stop).
- Being transparent about uncertainty, trade-offs, and evolving priorities, including what will not be addressed in the current cycle.
- Communicating that not all activities will lead to immediate or scalable solutions.
- Engaging funders and partners in ongoing dialogue about what success looks like in adaptive work.
- Where possible, sharing short learning updates during the cycle to make progress visible.

5.4. Avoiding extractive research and consultation fatigue

Education systems in many contexts are subject to repeated studies, consultations, and pilots that extract information without delivering tangible value to participants. DBIR explicitly seeks to avoid this pattern. In practice, this means:

- Ensuring that system actors benefit directly from participation through learning, reflection, or practical outputs.
- Treating data and insights as jointly owned rather than externally extracted; validating findings with participants and ensuring that findings are in accessible and usable formats for intended users.

- Being mindful of the time and effort required from participants, particularly at sub-national levels, by embedding activities into existing meetings and limiting repeat consultations where possible.

5.5. Navigating institutional constraints and political contexts

UDI (and research more broadly) do not operate in neutral environments. Institutional mandates, political incentives, and organisational risk aversion all shape what can be discussed, tested, or changed. Ethical DBIR practice, therefore, involves:

- Understanding institutional constraints and respecting formal lines of authority.
- Avoiding placing system actors in positions that expose them to undue political or professional risk.
- Being sensitive to how findings are communicated and to whom.
- Recognising when adaptation, rather than confrontation, is the most responsible course of action.

5.6. Reflexivity and learning within the UDI DBIR teams

Finally, ethical DBIR requires reflexivity by those who design and facilitate the work. UDI's DBIR approach encourages teams to:

- Regularly reflect on their own assumptions and positionality.
- Examine how their actions influence system dynamics.
- Document not only successes but also tensions and failures, and translate them into specific adaptations for the next cycle.
- Use learning to adapt facilitation, engagement, and design choices across cycles, including peer exchange across country teams where possible.

6. Looking ahead: DBIR across cycles, countries, and systems

As the Unlocking Data Initiative progresses, DBIR provides a unifying framework for learning over time, across geographies and system levels. Rather than treating each country engagement as a standalone intervention, UDI's DBIR approach enables cumulative learning, adaptive scaling, and the translation of locally grounded insights into regional and pan-African public goods, e.g., open-source toolkits, evidence synthesis and learning briefs, digital platforms and repositories.

6.1. DBIR as a mechanism for adaptive scaling

Within UDI, scaling is understood as a learning-led and adaptive process, not a simple replication of fixed models or tools. DBIR supports adaptive scaling by:

- Identifying core functions and principles that underpin effective data use (e.g., shared sensemaking, task-linked capacity development, coordination across actors).
- Distinguishing these transferable elements from context-specific design features that require local adaptation.
- Allowing solutions to evolve incrementally across DBIR cycles as system readiness, capacity, and institutional alignment increase.
- Generating evidence on implementation conditions and pathways, rather than focusing only on end-state outcomes.

6.2. Learning across countries and contexts

Cross-country learning within UDI does not rely on direct replication. Instead, learning travels through translation, comparison, and dialogue. Some mechanisms include:

- Cross-country synthesis products that surface common patterns and divergent experiences.
- Peer exchange among country teams, policymakers, and partners.
- Shared design principles and frameworks informed by multiple contexts.
- Regional reflection spaces where learning can be interrogated and adapted.

6.3. Role of regional and Pan-African Communities of Learning

Regional and pan-African CoLs are central to sustaining and amplifying DBIR learning beyond individual country engagements. These communities:

- Create durable platforms for peer learning and mutual support.
- Enable collective reflection on shared challenges, such as equity, inclusion, and sub-national data use.
- Support the diffusion of design principles and practices across contexts.
- Strengthen the legitimacy and visibility of locally generated evidence.

By connecting national experiences to regional dialogue, CoLs help embed DBIR insights within broader education and evidence ecosystems.

6.4. Positioning UDI's DBIR approach as a transferable public good

Over time, UDI's work generates value that extends beyond the Initiative itself. By documenting processes, principles, and learning, UDI positions its DBIR approach as a transferable public good that can inform other education reforms, research programmes, and data-use initiatives. This includes:

- Openly accessible guidance notes, frameworks, and synthesis products;
- Reusable design principles for strengthening education data ecosystems;
- Evidence on how system change unfolds in practice;
- Lessons on managing complexity, power, and adaptation in reform efforts.

Positioning DBIR outputs as public goods reinforces UDI's commitment to collective learning and contributes to the global knowledge base on strengthening foundational learning in education systems. Moreover, this has important implications for long-term impact, including by encouraging investment in:

- Local leadership and ownership of learning processes;
- Institutionalisation of CoPs and CoLs;
- Alignment with national priorities and planning cycles;
- Ongoing reflection and adaptation as systems evolve.

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